

Demonstration plant for testing and development at IVAR and Hias

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ABSTRACT

Deliverable D1.3 “Demonstration plant for testing and development at IVAR and Hias is part of Task 1.3 – “Fertiliser and soil improver by waste and wastewater resource recovery, Hamar and Stavanger, Norway”, led by NTNU, IVAR and Hias with contribution from HØST, Sirkula and Hias How20, in WP1 - Demonstrations of water-smart solutions. This Deliverable aims at demonstrating the technical plants for testing and development at IVAR (enhanced removal of suspended solids (SS) prior to biological treatment by dissolved air flotation or drum filters combined with polymer dosage), and HIAS (a sludge processing line for recovery of P from the EBPR sludge) built and ready for use as part of T1.3.1 and T1.3.2, respectively.

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1 Introduction

In WIDER UPTAKE, demonstration activities are covered by WP1. These activities ensure the application of water smart solutions in batch/pilot and real scale.

Within WP1, NTNU together with IVAR and Hias are the lead beneficiaries of T1.3 “Fertiliser and soil improver by waste and wastewater resource recovery, Hamar and Stavanger, Norway”. The activities will be conducted on the demonstration wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in Stavanger (IVAR) and Hamar (Hias).

In particular, the following tasks have to be achieved:

- T1.3.1: Wastewater treatment (Enhanced Biological Phosphorus Removal and optimised pre-treatment)
- T1.3.2: Resource recovery (struvite and biogas)
- T1.3.3: Value chains for recovered struvite and biogas

This document summarizes the preparation activities carried out by IVAR and Hias related to Deliverable D1.3 “Demonstration plant for testing and development at IVAR and Hias”. The technical plants for testing and development at IVAR (enhanced removal of suspended solids (SS) prior to biological treatment by dissolved air flotation or drum filters combined with polymer dosage), and HIAS (a sludge processing line for recovery of P from the EBPR sludge) are completed and ready for use as part of T1.3.1 and T1.3.2, respectively.

2 WWTP at IVAR (Stavanger)

IVAR IKS is a publicly company owned by 15 municipalities in the Rogaland county, South-West Norway. The activities are supply of water, treatment of wastewater and handling and treatment of solid waste for the 15 municipalities, serving a population of about 350000.

Within the areas of wastewater treatment, sludge treatment, handling, and treatment of solid organic waste the company has invested in new plants during the recent years. All processes are designed and operated for maximizing reuse of energy and nutrients.

The wastewater treatment plants have been retrofitted for optimum energy recovery by enhanced removal of suspended solids (SS) prior to biological treatment. Two main approaches, located at two different sites (Grødaland, IVAR-GD, and Sentralrenseanlegget nord-Jæren, IVAR-SNJ) are as follows:

1. IVAR-GD: Polymer precipitation along with dissolved air flotation (DAF) of wastewater influenced by food industry with high fat content, where flotation is the most suitable solution.
2. IVAR-SNJ: Primary filtration of domestic wastewater by drum filters with 100 µm pores. Polymer addition is planned to enhance SS separation.

2.1 Flotation unit at IVAR-GD

To facilitate enhanced removal of suspended solids (SS) prior to biological wastewater treatment, Grødaland was retrofitted with a Dissolved air flotation (DAF) unit with the possibility to add coagulating/flocculating chemicals. The treatment consists of two separate lines, each equipped with chemical addition and mixing, dispersion pumps, floatation tank, sludge scrapers (top & bottom) and sludge screws. Each line has a capacity of 100 l/s.

Chemical addition facilitates enhanced SS removal by coagulating and flocculating the particles (colloidal and suspended solids) in the wastewater. An inline mixer, immediately downstream the point of dosing, provides good mixing of the chemical with the wastewater. The dispersion pumps create micro bubbles by introducing air-saturated dispersion water into the process. The flocculated particles adhere to the bubbles and floats to the surface where they create a sludge blanket (Figure 1). The sludge blanket is removed by sludge scrapes (Figure 2) before the sludge is transferred to a small tank by screws (Figure 3). From the tank the sludge is pumped into a larger storage tank. Particles that settle on the bottom of the floatation tanks are removed by bottom scrapes and transferred to the sludge storage tank by pumps.

Figure 1: Flocculated SS floating to the surface starting to create a sludge blanket

Figure 2: Sludge blanket with the sludge scrape

Figure 3: Sludge screws transporting the sludge

This part is completed and today the DAF is operated with the addition of a polymer, and the chemical dosing has been optimized to remove approx. 60 % of SS in inlet wastewater (inlet wastewater contains 550 mg/L SS). Chemical dosing (l/h) is controlled by the flow (l/s) of incoming wastewater.

2.2 Primary filtration unit at IVAR-SNJ

2.2.1 Process description

Figure 4: HydroTech drum filters at IVAR SNJ (Photo: Kjetil Birkedal Pedersen, IVAR)

The filter system (Figure 4) is composed of 20 HydroTech drum filters with 100 μm pores. The filters are evenly distributed on each side of a distribution channel. The inlet to the filters is through the centre of the drum, and the filtered wastewater flows through the filters, while particles larger than 100 μm are retained on the screens.

The primary sludge accumulating on the filter cloth reduces the hydraulic throughput of the filters, and the level in the channel increases unless the filters are back flushed. Back flushing of the filters is controlled by a set point for the water level in the channel, enabling a pressure drop of 150–200 mm over the filter cloth. The filters are washed in groups of four, the factor T-delay determining flushing frequency. This factor determines the time interval between back wash start for subsequent filter groups and will vary inversely with the distribution channel water level. Consequently, the filters are flushed more/less frequently as the channel water level is increased/reduced. If the T-delay reached the minimum value and the level in the channel continues to rise, the wastewater will eventually overflow into the biological treatment stage.

The filters are back flushed with process water at 6 bars, distributed over 60 nozzles located on the outside of the filter cloth. Accumulated sludge is flushed from the inside of the cloth to an integrated sludge trough and pumped to a thickener system. Filtered wastewater is passed over an overflow and into the biological treatment stage.

Automatic hot water flushing at 80 bars is performed weekly on each filter. The filters are also equipped with a connection point and nozzles for chemical rinsing. Chemical cleaning of the screens is performed as needed, commonly every 2–3 months.

The filters have been prepared for polymer dosage.

Figure 5: Main principle of primary filtration

2.2.2 Performance of the filters

The main objective of the drum filters is to reduce the load on the biological treatment stage, thus reducing the energy requirement for aeration. The primary sludge removed in the filters also provides additional sludge for biogas production. Thus, the primary filtration both saves and yields energy. The filtration plant was designed to remove at least 50 % TSS at design flow, see Table 1.

Table 1: Design parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit
Q_{average}	6100	m ³ /h
Q_{design}	7400	m ³ /h
$Q_{\text{maksdesign}}$	10100	m ³ /h
Design load	33000	kg TSS/d
TSS removal @ Q_{design}	50	%
TSS removal @ $Q_{\text{maksdesign}}$	40	%

Figure 3 shows the filter plant performance between April 2020 and April 2021.

The average hydraulic load on the filters during this period was 4 850 m³/h, and the average TSS removal within this period was 52,6 %. As per Table 1, the filters performed according to design.

However, there have been major technical and mechanical challenges with the filter plant since the middle of 2018. These include (but are not limited to):

- Repeated mechanical issues with the back flushing nozzles, and malfunction of the hot water flushing system – both of which affected the capacity of the filtration plant
- Breakage and cracking of the structural elements in the filters
- Breakage of bolts in the main drive – probably due to imbalance in the filter drums caused by water entering through the cracks in the filter structure

Figure 6: Drum filter performance April 2020 - April 2021

These challenges have greatly delayed the optimization of the filter plant. However, the filtration plant has been prepared for polymer dosing as specified in the deliverable, and the initial intention of adding polymer to maximize the TSS removal is still relevant and will be implemented during the Wider Uptake project period. However, the mechanical issues listed above, need to be solved before any optimization efforts with polymer can be conducted.

3 WWTP at Hias (Hamar)

Hias IKS is a publicly company owned by 6 municipalities in the East of Norway. The largest owner is the city of Hamar, where also the WWTP is located. The activities are supply of water, treatment of wastewater and handling and treatment of solid waste for the 6 municipalities, serving a population of about 60000. The WWTP is treating wastewater from a population of 60000 with an additional industrial load.

The Hias WWTP was a chemical precipitation plant which now is being converted to an Enhanced Biological Phosphorus Removal (EBPR) process based on a new developed configuration with Moving Bed Biofilm Reactors (MBBR), followed by sludge treatment (Thermal Hydrolysis Process, THP, and Anaerobic Digestion, AD) and phosphorus recovery (struvite precipitation). See figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Flow diagram for the conversion of Hias WWTP to EBPR with P-recovery

3.1 Short status at Hias WWTP

The conversion of the Hias WWTP is completed with design key figures as given in figure 2 below.

Key figures		Key figures	
Design Capacity WWTP			
Primary and Chemical	90 000 person equivalent (pe)		
Biological	190 000 person equivalent (pe)		
Load			
Average	139 000 (pe)	THP	
Max	275 000(pe)	DS capacity	7 200 tonne DS/year
Hydraulic load		DS load	4 000 tonne DS/year
Dry weather	15 000 m3/day	DS content inlet	14 – 16% DS
Average	23 000 m3/day	Steam consumption	0.97 tonne/tonne DS
Maximum	70 000 m3/day	Digester	
Concentration inlet		Sludge load	4 000 tonne DS/year
Phosphorus, average	5 mg/l	Retention time	28 days
Phosphorus, max	10 mg/l	pH	7.6 – 7.7
COD, average	450 mg/l	DS content inlet	10 – 11%
COD, max	1600 mg/l	DS content outlet	5.5 – 6.0%
Demands of purification		DS reduction	50%
Phosphorus	0,4 mg/l	VS reduction	63%
BOD	25 mg/l	Dewatering	
COD	125 mg/l	Capacity	4 000 tonne DS/year
		DS content	35 – 38%

Figure 2. Key figures for the converted Hias WWTP after completion.

A flow diagram of the completed new Hias WWTP is shown in figure 3. It comprises of a primary clarifier followed by a novel Enhanced Biological Phosphorus Removal (EBPR) process based on a Moving Bed

Biofilm Reactor (MBBR) process with a disk filter for sludge separation. The sludge is then treated in a reactor for phosphorus and magnesium release before it is dewatered. The phosphorus-rich reject water is sent to the struvite reactor, while the solids is mixed with the sludge from the primary clarifier. This mixed sludge is dewatered and treated in a Thermal Hydrolysis Process (THP) together with external delivered sludge before it all goes to Anaerobic Digestion (AD). The bio-solids after AD are dewatered and the solids are used as soil improver/organic fertilizer, while the reject water is transferred to the struvite reactor. The solids from the struvite reactor are washed and dried to produce pure struvite.

Figure 3. Flow diagram of the completed new Hias WWTP.

Part of the “old” chemical precipitation plant have been converted to a storm water treatment facility.

3.2 Sludge processing line for recovery of P

The part of deliverable D1.3 which Hias is responsible for, consist of a sludge processing line for recovery of P from the EBPR sludge (the struvite reactor). The P-recovery system consist of a Pearl 2K reactor from Ostara with the necessary elements and add-ons, such as magnesium trap, dewatering, washing, drying, etc (see figure 4).

Figure 4. Pearl K2 from Ostara, struvite reactor system installed at Hias WWTP.

The Pearl K2 struvite reactor system which is installed at Hias WWTP has a production capacity 250 kg PO₄-P/day. The entire P-recovery system was installed, completed and ready for use in January 2023 (see figure 5). Successful test production has been conducted, and the system will gradually be put in full operation the coming months.

Figure 5. The Pearl 2K struvite reactor system after installation at Hias WWTP.

4 Conclusions

This report summarizes the activity by IVAR and Hias related to D1.3 “Demonstration plant for testing and development at IVAR and Hias”. All the activities in D1.3 have been completed.

